
THOUGHT BEHIND INDIA THAT IS BHARAT

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ABSTRACT

"India that is Bharat" is the action of enclosing the essence of India's historical and constitutional evolution, representing the many aspects, identity and diverse cultural tapestry of the nation. Rooted in the discussions of the Constituent Assembly during the drafting of India's Constitution, this phrase reflects the assembly's deliberations on unifying the pluralistic ethos of the country with its constitutional framework. The debates highlighted the significance of recognizing India's dual nomenclature and acknowledging its unity in diversity. It symbolizes the diverse cultural roots of the nation, integrating the ancient civilization of Bharat with the modern, diverse outline of India. It embodies the constitutional vision that upholds unity while celebrating the cultural, linguistic, and ethnic diversity of the country. The debates underscored the importance of harmonizing traditional values with modern governance principles, ensuring equitable representation and fostering national cohesion. "India that is Bharat" stands as a testament to India's rich history, cultural richness, and inclusive constitutional ideas.

I. INTRODUCTION

The phrase "India that is Bharat" reverberates through the corridors of India's constitutional history, signifying the union of diverse identities within the framework of a single nation. As the Constituent Assembly embarked on the difficult task of drafting the Indian Constitution, this phrase emerged as a testament to India's layered cultural tapestry and pluralistic ethos. It is the action enclosing the spirit of unity in diversity, acknowledging the coexistence of multiple historical narratives that constitute the Indian subcontinent. Rooted in ancient civilization and mythology, Bharat represents the historical legacy and traditional nature of India. It reflects the continuity of culture, traditions, and knowledge systems passed down through generations,

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embodying the essence of an ancient civilization. On the other hand, India symbolizes the modern, diverse, and dynamic nation-state shaped by colonial legacies, democratic aspirations, and socio-cultural amalgamation.

The discussions within the Constituent Assembly reflected the resonance between "India" and "Bharat," emphasizing the need to honour this duality within the constitutional framework. Visionaries and constitution drafters struggle with the task of balancing traditional values and contemporary governance models, ensuring that the Constitution would reflect the variety of cultures, languages, and religions cohabiting the nation.

II. HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

1. Ancient Roots

The concept of "Bharat" finds its roots in ancient Indian scriptures, particularly in epic narratives like the Mahabharata and Ramayana. According to Hindu mythology, Bharata was an ancient king and a forebear of the Kuru dynasty. The term "Bharatavarsha" referred to the Indian subcontinent, which was believed to be named after King Bharata.

2. Cultural Heritage and Unity

Over millennia, India evolved as a melting pot of diverse cultures, languages, religions, and traditions. The phrase "India that is Bharat" symbolizes the amalgamation of these multifaceted identities into a unified whole. It reflects India's natural unity in diversity, highlighting the coexistence of various beliefs, practices, and ways of life.

3. National Movement and Quest for Independence

During India's struggle for independence, leaders like Mahatma Gandhi and Jawaharlal Nehru invoked the idea of "India that is Bharat." They emphasized the revival of India's ancient wisdom and spiritual values as a means to unite the country against colonial rule. The phrase became a powerful expression, symbolizing India's inherent unity and diversity, driving the collective consciousness of the freedom movement.

4. Constitutional Debates

The phrase "India that is Bharat" represents a deep acknowledgement of the country's diverse cultural, social, and historical fabric. During the constitutional debates, the

members of the Constituent Assembly embraced this phrase to encapsulate the essence of India's composite identity. It signified unity amid diversity prevalent across the nation. The assembly aimed to highlight that while "India" symbolizes the modern, progressive, and forward-looking aspects of the nation, "Bharat" represents its ancient, traditional, and timeless values. This duality aimed to recognize and honour the coexistence of multiple cultures, languages, customs, and traditions within the framework of one nation.

The thought behind using this phrase reflected the assembly's commitment to acknowledging and celebrating India's unity in diversity. It sought to emphasize the coalescence of different ideologies, beliefs, and practices into a unified identity, fostering a sense of pride in the country's rich heritage while moving forward with a shared vision for progress and development.

5. Contemporary Relevance

In contemporary times, "India that is Bharat" signifies the synthesis of India's glorious past with its aspirations for the future. It encapsulates the idea of a pluralistic society that cherishes its cultural diversity, promotes unity amidst differences, and aspires for progress and development while being rooted in its age-old ethos.

III. THE CONSTITUTION ASSEMBLY DEBATE ON “INDIA THAT IS BHARAT”

The first debate on Article 1 was to begin on November 17, 1948. However, at the suggestion of Govind Ballabh Pant, the discussion on the name was postponed to a later date. On September 17, 1949, Dr B R Ambedkar presented to the House the final version of the provision, which included both 'Bharat' and 'India'. During the constitutional assembly debates in 1949, the phrase "India, that is Bharat" was introduced in the Preamble of the Indian Constitution. It reflects the diverse cultural and historical identity of the nation. The choice of using both "India" and "Bharat" was to recognize the country's rich heritage and linguistic diversity. The constitutional assembly aimed to create a document that acknowledged and respected the pluralistic nature of the newly independent nation.

The debates ended with the addition of ‘Bharat’ to Article 1(1). The Article currently reads ‘India, that is Bharat, shall be a Union of States.’ A row over the name of the country had erupted with a

G-20 dinner invitation going out in the name of the 'President of Bharat'. Some of the Constituent Assembly Members had wanted the term 'States' in Article 1 to be replaced with 'Pradesh' but Pandit Nehru had objected, saying, "Pradesh is a word which has no definition. No one knows what it means... It is a very good word, and gradually it may begin to get a significance, and then of course it can be used either in the Constitution or otherwise. At the present moment, the normal use of the word varies in hundreds of different ways and the word 'State' is infinitely more precise, more definite, not only for the outside world but even for us." On 14 August 1947 at midnight, India became independent. Two weeks later, on 29 August 1947, the Constituent Assembly, which had been meeting since December 1946, set up a Drafting Committee under the Chairmanship of B.R. Ambedkar. From February 1948 to November 1949, the members of the Constituent Assembly examined the draft, moving and discussing in the process almost 2,500 amendments. On 26 November 1949, they finally adopted the Constitution of India and signed it on 24 January 1950. On 26 January 1950, the Constitution of India officially came into force, and the Constituent Assembly became the Provisional Parliament of India until the first general elections of 1952.

IV. THE VIEWS OF THE EMINENT CONSTITUTIONAL DRAFTERS

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar

As one of the chief architects of the Indian Constitution, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar envisioned India as a nation where the concepts of "India" and "Bharat" complemented each other. He acknowledged the rich cultural diversity and historical heritage that "Bharat" represented and aimed to integrate it into the modern democratic framework of "India." Ambedkar believed that acknowledging India's historical roots and diverse cultures would form the principle of a progressive and inclusive India.

Dr. Rajendra Prasad

Dr. Rajendra Prasad's vision for "India that is Bharat" revolved around preserving India's rich cultural legacy and historical traditions while ensuring the nation's growth and progress in the modern world. He advocated for a balanced approach that harmonized the ancient wisdom of India with the principles of democracy and governance in the Constitution.

Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel

Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel, known for his vital role in integrating princely states into India, envisioned a nation where the diversity of cultures and traditions coexisted harmoniously under the unified identity of India. Patel envisioned "India that is Bharat" as a powerful representation of the country's unity in diversity. He believed that acknowledging both "India" and "Bharat" reflected the coexistence of modernity and tradition, acknowledging the nation's rich historical heritage alongside its aspirations for progress and development.

Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru

Jawaharlal Nehru, the first Prime Minister of India, perceived "India that is Bharat" as an amalgamation of India's ancient cultural heritage and the aspirations of a modern, forward-looking nation. His vision was to preserve India's ancient traditions while steering the country towards scientific and industrial progress. Nehru emphasized the need to combine the spiritual and cultural legacy of India with modern principles of democracy, scientific inquiry, and technological advancement.

K.M Munshi

Munshi's perspective on "India that is Bharat" encapsulated the idea of continuity and change, urging the nation to progress while staying rooted in its rich cultural legacy. He emphasized that embracing this dual identity would contribute to building a strong, inclusive, and culturally vibrant India.

Alladi Krishnaswamy Iyer

He envisioned "India that is Bharat" as a harmonious amalgamation of tradition and modernity, where the nation's cultural ethos and values remain integral while embracing the dynamics of a rapidly changing world. For Iyer, this phrase signified the continuity of India's timeless cultural heritage amidst the waves of modernity, leading to a harmonious and inclusive national identity.

Rabindranath Tagore

India's eminent poet and philosopher says "Bharat is the heartbeat of India, pulsating with the rhythm of unity in diversity." This quote symbolizes Bharat as the core element of India, representing the harmonious coexistence of diverse cultures, languages, and traditions. It

highlights the unity found amidst the country's rich diversity, portraying Bharat as the pulsating rhythm that unifies the nation.

Some other leaders' views say

“India is Bharat, Bharat is India, the two are one and it represents the unity of our country.”

This quote reflects the interconnectedness and unity between India's dual identities - "India" as the modern nation and "Bharat" as its traditional essence. It emphasizes that despite being referred to by different names, they symbolize the integral unity of the nation, promoting a sense of oneness among its diverse population.

V. LEGISLATIVE INTENTION BEHIND “INDIA THAT IS BHARAT”

The legislative intention behind the topic "India that is Bharat" within the constitutional debates was aimed at addressing several critical aspects integral to the formation of India as a democratic republic.

1. Unity in Diversity

The phrase enclosed the essence of India's diverse cultural, linguistic, religious, and ethnic heritage. The framers of the Constitution recognized this diversity as the nation's strength and sought to embed this principle within the legislative fabric. The intention was to build a society that respects and cherishes differences while fostering a sense of unity among its people.

2. Synthesis of Historical and Modern Values

The legislative intention was to harmonize the rich historical legacy of India with the modern ideals of democracy, secularism, and justice. The Constituent Assembly deliberated on incorporating provisions that upheld India's ancient wisdom, ethical values, and cultural heritage while embracing progressive principles essential for a modern democratic society.

3. Ensuring Pluralism and Inclusivity

Another legislative intention was to create a constitution that ensures equal rights, opportunities, and justice for all citizens, irrespective of their diverse backgrounds. The framers aimed to

establish a society that respects pluralism encourages inclusivity, and safeguards the interests of minority communities, ensuring their representation and protection.

4. Strengthening National Identity

The constitutional debates aimed to reinforce a strong national identity rooted in India's diverse cultural ethos. The intention was to cultivate a sense of pride and belonging among citizens, emphasizing the shared values and historical heritage that bind the nation together despite its multifarious diversity.

VI. CONCLUSION

The idea of "India that is Bharat" encapsulates the essence of unity in diversity, the harmonious blend of tradition and modernity, and the richness of a culture over centuries. This profound notion signifies more than mere geographical or political demarcations; it represents the symbiotic relationship between India's ancient heritage, encapsulated in the term "Bharat," and its dynamic, progressive identity as "India." Throughout the constitutional debates and beyond, this concept echoed the sentiments of the nation's leaders, emphasizing integral unity despite the diversity. It celebrates India's pluralistic ethos, where various languages, cultures, and traditions coalesce into a vibrant tapestry. The notion of "India that is Bharat" isn't merely a linguistic juxtaposition; it's a philosophical articulation that reverberates with the core values and ethos of the Indian subcontinent. It stands as a testament to the unbroken cultural continuum, showcasing the resilience of a civilization that cherishes its ancient roots while embracing the aspirations of a modern, inclusive society. Its processes are shaped by broad socio-political conditions and can be studied from several angles. In this paper, I have adopted a cultural history perspective. My purpose has been to look at some of the inherited discourses on 'Bhārata' both prior to and at the time of its official equation with 'India' in the Constitution of 1950. To begin with I attempted to characterize the memory that was taken in by those who in the 19th century used the name Bhārata to refer to the geographical, political and administrative entity that the colonial power called 'India'. The evidence presented shows that it was the Puranic memory of a naturally bounded (sea, mountains) and specifically socially organized territory where human beings could fulfil the specific sets of socio-religious duties required to maintain their cultural identity. That Bhārata—a cultural space whose unity was to be found in the social order of dharma—was a pre-national

construction and not a national project. Then I argued that at the time of independence, India and Bhārata were equally worthy candidates to baptize the newly-born nation, along with 'Hindustan'. But the opening article of the Constitution discarded Hindustan and registered the nation under a dual and bilingual identity: 'India, that is Bharat'. One name was to be used as the equivalent or the translation of the other as exemplified on the cover of the national passport, where the English 'Republic of India' corresponds to the Hindi 'Bhārata gaṇarājya', or, perhaps even more telling, on India postage stamps, where the two words Bhārata and India are collocated. Pursuing the history of the reception of the Constitutional equation of Bharat and India in all its social and political complexities was beyond the scope of my enquiry. I have merely pointed to two contemporary phenomena: the name Hindustan has continued to be widely used despite, or maybe thanks to, its plurality of meanings and the implication of the equivalence of Bharat with India has remained a subject of debate. It is likely that all these names will continue to be interpreted to fit new circumstances, to give new meanings to India's national identity, an ongoing, open-ended process.